
IMPLICATION OF ENCROACHMENT ON IFELODUN LOCAL GOVERNMENT WETLANDS AND WAY OUT

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the effects of wetlands in Osun State's Ifelodun Local Government Area and warn stakeholders about the risks involved in specific activities that could harm the wetlands. The purpose of this is to assess the changes that have occurred in Ifelodun LGA wetlands from 2002 to 2022. The data was obtained from remote sensing data using Landsat TM 2002 and Landsat ETM 2022, covering the distribution of wetland costs and accession from 2002 to 2022. Questionnaires were also used to gather data for this research work. Residents, key agencies, state and local governments have to take on the responsibility of ensuring the sustainable expansion of the area without compromising its natural and valuable wetlands in the public interest.

Keywords: *Wetland, Delineation, Aquifer, Water recharge and discharge, spatiotemporal Changes.*

INTRODUCTION

According to the Ramsar Convention (2007), a wetland is any region of marsh, swamp, peatland, or water body that is marine in nature, artificial or permanent, flowing or stagnant, fresh, brackish, or bitter, and has a depth of less than six meters. In addition, they may include riparian and coastal areas adjacent to wetlands and islands, or water bodies about six meters deeper in wetlands (Ramsar Convention, 2007). According to Keddy (2010), wetlands are considered ecosystems that develop when flooding produces soil that is dominated by anaerobic processes. These processes then allow the fatty biota, particularly plant roots, to adapt to the flood. The United States Environmental Protection Agency (USEPA, 2009) defines a wetland as an area of land or land on or near land that is flooded throughout the year or at different times of the year. According to McCarten et al. (2010), a wetland is groundwater or a combination of groundwater flowing from surrounding waters. Hu, Liu, Zheng, and Xie (2018) defined wetlands as "kidneys of the world" and "biological repositories" due to their important features such as water, nutrients, nutrient abundance, and biodiversity. In nature, they are by definition natural collectors of rainwater: They are on or near the earth. Globally, wetlands cover approximately 5–10% of the world's land (Mitsch and Gosselink, 2007). Approximately 1.28 billion hectares, but no estimates are believed to be available. Often considered waste but crucial to human survival on Mother Earth, these include: mitigating the impact of floods, improving landscapes, recharging ground water; sustaining frozen shorelines, sediment and nutrient retention and export, water purification, biodiversity reservoirs, wetland products, cultural values.; natural water development, flood protection, coastal erosion control; recreation and beauty, and free use of natural resources. The relationship of man with his environment always changes over time, depending on his understanding and perception of the physical environment. However, the natural environment often provides different resources; therefore, man begins to view his environment as a source of satisfaction for his needs and therefore constantly seeks ways to extract resources from the environment. Unfortunately, this leads to the neglect of environmental monitoring of many environmental stressors (Ezeaku et al., 2008; Jimoh et al., 2012). The study area numbered has some wetlands, and due to population growth, agriculture, and the government inability to control urban development, Ifelodun Local Government Area has been expanded unplanned, resulting in more land acquisition in wetlands. . The beaches in Ifelodun Town have been severely affected in recent years. A visit to the wetlands reveals many new activities that indicate a significant recent disturbance. These activities include residential and commercial, car washing, farming, pig farming, poultry farming, fishing, gardening, etc. Vegetation has decreased, and the wetlands are now more prone to flooding during heavy rains than before. All of these activities put pressure on the wetlands, affecting their ecological functions and damaging the wetlands. Uncontrolled urban expansion and unsystematic agricultural activities have a significant impact on environmental quality in many areas. Opoku (2013) has suggested that population growth in coastal areas is often associated with more impermeable areas. Changes in water flow are accompanied by a decrease in the ability of these systems to control water flow. Studies show that, like many coastal cities around the world, little is known about the actual impact of human activities on the coast. In this case, the exact nature of these changes is often unknown and unreported. Taiwo and Areola (2009) provided information on changing wetlands in selected coastal areas of Lagos; a comprehensive study assessing various changes in wetlands in Lagos/Lekki Lagoon has yet to be reported. Almost all types of wetlands have been studied from satellite images. In some studies, multi-temporal assessments often help in classifying wetlands and distinguishing them from other land cover classes. The wetlands studied with knowledge of the area include marshes, swamps, lagoons, coastal tidal marshes, mangroves and other

coastal wetlands, marshes and swamps, inland freshwater marshes, forested wetlands or marshes, open water, wet meadows; and submerged aquatic vegetation (Obiefunaet. , 2013). Ajibola et al. (2012) claim that the wetland ecology has been severely destroyed for development reasons due to land competition. Due to increased pressure on the area's existing land due to Boko Haram and Fulani herdsmen threats, as well as recent development in Osogbo, the state capital that borders the study area, and the desperate need for new housing and land, people are being forced to encroach into the wetlands. Wetlands in the Ifelodun Local Government Area have been severely damaged by conversion to agricultural and residential construction uses.

This is evident in places like Obaagun, Eko-Ende, Eko-Ajala, and Ikirun. In opposition to the goal of preserving the wetlands, wetlands along the Ikirun and Eko-Ende axis are mostly destroyed and invaded by ongoing sand filling and conversion for uses that bring about residential and commercial benefits. The problem of wetlands encroaching in the research area has not been addressed by the Act of 1992 or the NESREA Act No. 25 of 2007. Up until now, no study has offered the required details to explain why people are intruding into the wetlands in Osun State's Ifelodun Local Government Area. This widening gap must be filled, which is the basis for this study's justification.

Landmass, Climate, and Classification of Forests:

The Local Government encompasses around 136.5 square kilometers of territory. The Ifelodun area experiences a tropical environment with an average annual temperature of roughly 26.10 degrees Celsius and 1241 millimeters of precipitation. It is January that is the driest. In January, there is 9 mm of precipitation. The highest point of precipitation, with an average of 202mm, occurs in September. It is surrounded by savannah vegetation and tropical deciduous woodland. It is able to grow food and cash crops because of its favorable climate and vegetation.

This research project aims to investigate the wetlands' invasion in Ifelodun LGA, Osun State.

- i. Mapping the spatial distribution of wetlands in the research region is one of the specific goals.
- ii. Research how the subject area's wetland pattern has changed throughout time.
- iii. Assess how the loss of wetlands affects the vegetation cover pattern in the research area
- iv. Look at anticipated patterns of land use/land cover changes in the area

STUDY AREA

Ifelodun LGA is in Osun State, Nigeria, with its headquarter in Ikirun. Ifelodun is situated east of the Greenwich Meridian and between 07.00 and 08.80 degrees north of the equator. Bounded by Odo-Otin Local Government Area in the north; by Boripe Local Government Area in the East; and in the south-west by the Olorunda Local Government Area, which has 96,748 residents, according to the 2006 census. Yoruba make up the majority of the population in Ifelodun Local Government Area, and agricultural production continues to be the backbone of the local economy. Cocoa, kolanut, oil palm products, cashew, coffee, and food crops like yam, cocoyam, cassava, sugarcane, groundnut, maize, pepper, and others are among the tree crops they cultivate. The total land area governed by the Local Government is approximately 136.5 square kilometers. The environment is tropical in nature, while normal yearly temperature in Ifelodun region is around 26.10 Celsius with around 1241mm of precipitation yearly. The driest month is January. January receives 9 millimeters of precipitation. In September, the precipitation arrives at its top, with a normal of 202mm. It is

surrounded by tropical deciduous forest and savannah vegetation. It is able to produce food and cash crops thanks to its favorable climate and vegetation. Ifelodun Neighborhood Government Region is on a generally marsh with delicate undulations in some part having Otin Stream in Eko-ende as the greatest of the waterways in the Nearby Government with more modest feeders which incorporate Osere, Ontoki, Ponjo streaming in Ikirun and its environs as well as some others somewhere else in the neighborhood government region. A significant portion of the area is waterlogged, easily flooded during the rainy season, and there are a lot of wetlands because of the area's low relief.

Figure 1: Map of Osun State

Figure 2: Map of Ifelodun LGA

An area of Wetland being prepared for farming in Eko-Ende

portion of Wetland already converted to fish pond along Eko-Ende Road Ikirun

Figure 3: An area of wetland being prepared for farming and Fishing in Eko-Ende

Figure 4: Residential houses within a wetland area at Oke- Afo area, Ikirun

METHODOLOGY

In order to gather data on the study area, this research integrates remote sensing techniques with a Geographic Information System (GIS) and PC-based image processing and analysis utilizing ArcGIS10.4 software. Both topographical maps and satellite imagery were used to map the degree of urbanization and encroachment on the wetlands owned by the Ifelodun Local Government.

Table 1: The Land-use Classification Scheme used in the study

S/No	CLASS	DESCRIPTION
1	Scattered development	The construction of additional homes, either standalone or inside a subdivision, at a certain separation from the current built-up regions.
2	Mixed forests	Agricultural areas, and other types of vegetation.
3	Built-up Areas	Portions of land used for residential development, as well as other urban arrears caused by human activity, such as marketplaces, schools, banks, highways, and railroads.
4	Fringe Vegetation	Peripheral Plants Groves, solitary trees, shrubs, and grasslands.
5	Scattered development	The construction of additional homes, either standalone or inside a subdivision, at a certain separation from the current built-up areas.
6	Cultivations	The process of cultivating a plant on land. For instance, farms, etc.
7	Grasses	Any of a broad range of green plants featuring stalks of clustered flowers, long, thin leaves, and jointed stems; grass that is grown over land, such as a lawn.

1. Demographic Analysis of Household Heads

Table 2: Towns in Ifelodun LGA, Osun State

<i>Town</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Ikirun	58	48.3
Eko-Ende	17	14.2
Eko-Ajala	15	12.5
Obaagun	30	25.0
Total	120	100.0

From table 2 above, it is observed that, Ikirun own has the highest number of the respondents of 58 (48.3%), Obaagun has 30 household heads (25.0%), Eko-Ende with 17 (12.5%) household heads and also Eko-Ajala has 15 (12.5%) of the respondents This indicates a wide distribution of questionnaires to the areas under investigation. Ikirun own has the highest number of household heads being the headquarters of Ifelodun Local Government Area and also have the highest population in the area of human population and landscape in the LGA.

Table 3: Gender of the Household Heads

<i>Gender</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
Male	73	60.8
Female	47	39.2
Total	120	100.0

As it can be seen from the table, a very balanced range of participants were contacted, suggesting that the investigators sought for data from a diverse range of respondents to validate the quality of the data collected.. As shown in the table above, 73(60.8%) respondents are male, and female are 47 (39.2%).

Table 4: Age Distribution of the Household Heads

<i>Age Range</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
26-35	9	7.5
36-45	18	15.0
46-55	36	30.0
56-65	30	25.0
66-75	24	20.0
76 and above	3	2.5
Total	120	100.0

Table 4 above, 9 (7.5%) of the household heads are between 26-35 years old, 18 (15.0%) are between the ages of 36-45, and 36 (30.0%) are between the ages of 46-55., 30 (25.0%) respondents are between 56-65 years old, 24 (20.0%) are of the ages 66-75 years old, 3 (2.5%) are of age 76 and above.

Table 5: Marital Status of the Household Heads

Marital Status	Frequency	Percent
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Single	8	6.7
Married	63	52.5
Widow / Widower	39	32.5
Divorced	10	8.3
Total	120	100.0

Table 5 above shows that the majority of the respondents are married, with 63 (52.5%), while only 8 (6.7) are singles, 39 (32.5%) are either widow or widower, and only 10 (8.3%) of the respondents are divorced.

Table 6: Religion of the Household Heads

Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Christianity	48	40.0
Islam	56	46.7
Traditional	16	13.3
Total	120	100.0

Table 6 above shows the religions of the household heads with 48 (40.0%) being Christians, while 56 (46.7%) are and only 16 (13.3%) are traditional worshipers.

Table 7: Educational Qualification of the respondents

Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
SSCE/WAEC	27	22.5
NCE/ND	30	25.0
HND/BSC	39	32.5
MASTER	21	17.5
PhD	3	2.5
Total	120	100.0

Above table 7 indicates that 3 (2.5%) respondents have PhD, 21 (17.5%) have master degrees, 39 (32.5%) bagged either HND or BSc., 30 (25.0%) respondents had NCE or ND certificates while only 27 (22.5%) of the household heads had either SSCE or WAEC qualifications.

Table 8: Occupations of the respondents

Profession	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Artisan	19	15.8
Famer	32	26.7
Gov. Worker	48	40.0
Trading	14	11.7
Others	7	5.8
Total	120	100.0

From Table 8 above, It is noted that most of the household heads, 48 (40.0%) are government workers with either the local, state or federal government. 19 (15.8%) are artisans, 32 (26.7%) are farmers, 14 (11.7%) are traders of one local goods or the other, and only 7 (5.8%) are for other occupations.

Table 9: Years of Residency of the Household Heads

Years of Residency	Frequency	Percentage (%)
1-5	11	9.2
6-10	30	25.0
11-15	25	20.8
16-20	20	16.7
21 and above	34	28.3
Total	120	100.0

Table above shows that majority of the household heads have been living in the community for over 10 years, some have spent 15, 20 and above 21 years.

Table 10: Environmental Practices of Households

Environmental Practices	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Climate change	22	18.3
Soil properties	12	10.0
Terrain	86	71.7
Total	120	100.0

Table 11: Human Activities that affects Wetlands Ecosystem

Human Activities	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Stream channelization	8	6.7
Dam Construction	3	2.5
Sewage/Refuse	82	68.3
Agricultural Practices	27	22.5
Total	120	100.0

Figure 5: Chart of the different Practices that affects Wetlands in Ifelodun LGA

Table 12: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.772 ^a	.596	.592	.459

a. Predictors: (Constant), Years of Residency of the Household Heads

Table 13: ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	36.625	1	36.625	173.970	.000 ^b
	Residual	24.842	118	.211		
	Total	61.467	119			

a. Dependent Variable: Human Activities that affects Wetlands Ecosystem of Ifelodun LGA

b. Predictors: (Constant), Years of Residency of the Household Heads

Table 14: Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	1.718	.111		15.543	.000
Years of Residency of the Household Heads	.409	.031	.772	13.190	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Human Activities that affects Wetlands Ecosystem of Ifelodun LGA

2. Spatio-Temporal Change Detection Analysis (S-TCDA)

The "area Analysis method" is the change detection technique applied in this study. This entails an analysis that displays the trend and rate of various land use (LU) changes during the evaluation period. The process of computing the change detection for each LU using area statistics is divided into three (3) stages. While several satellite data sets are available for this kind of study, NASA's Landsat imageries, which have a spatial resolution of 30 meters, are the specific ones that are employed. In order to create a baseline mapping for a sequential tracking of changes across various periods, topographic data for the years 2002, 2010, 2016, and 2022 were combined to create these products.

Wetland condition in the study area in 1984

Figure 1 shows the wetland's condition in 1984. It is evident from the map that wetlands were extensively dispersed throughout the research area. Urban development is not dominant (0.15%). The land use/land cover is summarized in Table 2.

Table 15: Land use/Land cover in 1984

Class, 1984	Sum_Area Sq	Percent (%)
Build-Up Areas	0.27	0.15
Mixed Forest	59.83	32.94
Water Bodies	18.25	10.05
Scattered Develop.	0.73	0.40
Ocean/Sea	6.18	3.40
Wetland Complex	88.45	48.70
Grasses	7.92	4.36
Total	181.63	100

Wetland condition in the study area in 2002

Table 16: Land use/Land cover in 2002

Class, 2002	Sum_Area Sq	Percent (%)
Build-Up Areas	5.98	3.29
Mixed Forest	42.13	23.20
Water Bodies	24.74	13.62
Scattered Develop.	32.62	17.96
Ocean/Sea	8.91	4.90
Wetland Complex	64.13	35.31
Grasses	3.12	1.72
Total	181.63	100

Between 1984 and 2002, the cover of the wetland complex dropped by 14%, from approximately 49% to approximately 35%, maintaining the downward trend. As can be shown later, some of the elements of the changes are discernible in the irregular developments and newly developing grassy areas.

Wetland condition in the study area in 2022

Table 17: Land use/ Land cover in 2022

Class, 2002	Sum_Area Sq	Percent (%)
Build-Up Areas	41.58	22.89
Mixed Forest	1.47	0.81
Water Bodies	19.25	10.60
Scattered Develop.	35.27	19.41
Ocean/Sea	12.13	6.68
Wetland Complex	52.67	29.0
Grasses	19.26	10.61
Total	181.63	100

Over this time, the area that is built up has grown to 41.58 km², or 22.89% of the total land area. In 2002, the built-up area component was only 3.29%.

Findings:

It is clear from the results in Tables 1 through 17 that the study area's wetlands are being encroached upon. The amount of land covered by wetlands has significantly decreased over the course of the research. In the research area, development may supplant alternative forms of land cover if this tendency is not investigated. For the ecosystem's and groundwater replenishment processes' correct operation, this study advises that the study area's natural environment be protected.

Conclusions

In the marsh of Ifelodun Local Government area, there were sporadic and persistent spatiotemporal alterations. They were discovered in the area's size, submersion, and vegetation. Climatic changes were attributed to alterations in the world, such as modifications in the patterns of precipitation. Due to building or exposed surfaces, the great bulk of the canal basin was gone. According to the survey, the wetland's most damaging land uses were those related to development, horticultural, and reject activities, such as crop cultivation and animal brushing, as these had occupied large portions of the area and were increasing the wetlands' exposed surface areas.

The main consideration adding to infringement on the wetland was the debasement and unfortunate checking of authorities that permitted bequest engineers to involve the terrains for development. This was likewise upheld by poor natural perspectives of both local area occupants and non-inhabitants. Individuals' food needs likewise energized infringement through cultivating and other horticultural practices.

Recommendations

The following suggestions were drawn from the discoveries and conclusions of the study. The Physical and Town Office is encouraged to:

1. Arrange seminars and make publications on appropriate structure allows and land use privileges, to unveil the overall mindful of fake allows that might be given by government authorities and conventional caretakers of grounds.
2. Set out on natural training through direct methodology into the periphery networks around the wetlands and furthermore by broad communications for the overall population.
3. Team up with the landowners of the terrains encompassing the wetland, the local government administrators, and other pertinent natural assurance organizations to implement ecological regulations, assents, and punishments against infringement on the we Set out on ecological instruction through direct methodology into the periphery networks around the wetlands and furthermore by broad communications for the overall population.
4. Support to the local government and relevant government agencies for real power to practice, endorses and execute natural assurance promotions and plans.

Family heads are additionally encouraged to:

1. Report all unlawful land uses of the wetlands to Local Government Authority and Physical and Town planning division for activity and change.
2. Cease from looking for deceitful structures and development grants from government authorities and offices.
3. Imbibe appropriate ecological practices and furthermore regard land client freedoms relating to the wetlands.

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